

NEUROPSYCHOLOGICAL DISORDERS IN MULTIPLE SCLEROSIS

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НЕЙРОПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ НАРУШЕНИЯ ПРИ РАССЕЯННОМ СКЛЕРОЗЕ

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TARQOQ SKLEROZ KASALLIGIDA NEYROPSIXOLOGIK BUZILISHLAR

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Abstract: Today, multiple sclerosis is one of the most widespread neurological diseases. As the disease progresses, patients experience not only motor system disorders but also neuropsychological disturbances, which become the leading symptoms. These symptoms negatively affect patients' daily lives and professional activities. In the early stages of the disease, both complete preservation of cognitive functions and significant impairments can be observed. Cognitive deficit in multiple sclerosis changes depending on the stage of the disease, just like other symptoms. Cognitive status may worsen during demyelination and improve during remission. Additionally, when assessing cognitive function, it is important to consider the selection of patients and the set of tests used. This article discusses the symptoms observed in patients with multiple sclerosis, neuropsychological disorders, particularly cognitive impairments, depression, and anxiety disorders. Today, multiple sclerosis is one of the most common neurological diseases. The leading signs in the course of the disease in patients are neuropsychiatric disorders. These symptoms negatively affect the lives and work of patients.

Keywords: Multiple sclerosis, cognitive disorders, neuropsychological tests, depression, anxiety.

Аннотация: На сегодняшний день рассеянный склероз является одной из наиболее распространённых неврологических болезней. В процессе

прогрессирования заболевания у пациентов наблюдаются не только нарушения двигательной системы, но и нейропсихологические расстройства, которые становятся ведущими симптомами. Эти симптомы оказывают негативное влияние на повседневную жизнь и профессиональную деятельность больных. На ранних стадиях заболевания можно наблюдать как полное сохранение когнитивных функций, так и их значительные нарушения. Когнитивный дефицит при рассеянном склерозе изменяется в зависимости от стадии заболевания, как и другие его симптомы. Когнитивный статус может ухудшаться в период демиелинизации и улучшаться в ремиссии. Кроме того, при оценке когнитивной функции важно учитывать выбор пациентов и набор тестов.

В этой статье рассматриваются симптомы, наблюдаемые у пациентов с рассеянным склерозом, нейропсихологические расстройства, в частности, когнитивные нарушения, депрессия и тревожные состояния.

Ключевые слова: Рассеянный склероз, когнитивные нарушения, нейропсихологические тесты, депрессия, тревожность.

Annotatsiya: Bugungi kunda tarqoq skleroz kasalligi nevrologik kasalliklar ichida keng ko'p tarqalgan kasalliklardan biri xisoblanadi. Kasallik kechish davomida bemorlarda nafaqat harakat tizimi, shuningdek neyropsixologik buzilishlar ham yetakchi belgilarni egallamoqda. Bu belgilar bemorning hayot va ish faoliyatiga ham o'z salbiy ta'sirini ko'rsatmoqda. Kasallikning erta davrlarida kognitiv funksiyaning to'liq saqlanishidan tortib, uning og'ir darajada buzilishigacha bo'lgan holatlarni kuzatish mumkin. Tarqoq skleroz kasalligida kognitiv yetishmovchilik ham kasallikning boshqa belgilari kabi kasallik davrlari davomida o'zgaradi. Kognitiv status demielinizatsiya jarayoning qo'zish davrida yomonlashishi va remissiyada yaxshilanishi mumkin. Shuningdek, kognitiv funktsiya faoliyatini baholashda tanlangan bemorlar va testlar to'plamlari ham ahamiyatga ega.

Ushbu maqolada tarqoq skleroz kasalligi bilan ogriqan bemorlarda kuzatiladigan belgilar, neyropsixologik buzilishlar, xususan, kognitiv buzilishlar, depressiya va xavotirlik holatlari haqida fikr yuritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Tarqoq skleroz, kognitiv buzilishlar, neyropsixologik testlar, depressiya, xavotirlik.

Multiple sclerosis (MS), the most prevalent neurological disability, is an autoimmune-mediated disorder that affects the central nervous system (CNS) and often leads to severe physical or cognitive incapacitation as well as neurological problems in young adults [1]. Multifocal zones of inflammation due to focal T-lymphocytic and macrophage infiltrations, and oligodendrocyte death are the primary causes of myelin sheath destruction [2]. that result in the formation of CNS plaques composed of inflammatory cells and their products, demyelinated and transected axons, and astrogliosis in both white and gray matter. These lesions can cross-talk

with the correct transmission of nerve impulses and lead to neuronal dysfunction such as autonomic and sensorimotor defects, visual disturbances, ataxia, fatigue, difficulties in thinking, and emotional problems [1].

Subtypes of MS are considered important not only for prognosis but also for treatment decisions and include: relapsing remitting MS (RRMS), primary progressive MS (PPMS), secondary progressive MS (SPMS), and progressive relapsing MS (PRMS). RRMS is the most common subtype (approximately 87%) which characterized by unpredictable acute attacks followed by periods of remission [3]. During RRMS, inflammatory attacks on myelin and nerve fibers occur. Activated immune cells cause lesions in the CNS which generate symptoms of visual impairments, tingling and numbness, episodic bouts of fatigue, intestinal and urinary system disorders, spasticity, and learning and memory impairment. Approximately 10-15% of MS patients are diagnosed with PPMS which largely affect the nerves of the spinal cord. PPMS patients tend to have fewer brain lesions. Induced symptoms include problems with walking, weakness, stiffness, and trouble with balance. Nearly 65% of patients with RRMS will subsequently develop SPMS which is considered the second phase of this disease. Many individuals experience increased weakness, intestinal and urinary system disorders, fatigue, stiffness, mental disorders, and psychological impairment. Finally, PRMS is the least common type of MS that occurs in approximately 5% of patients and is associated with symptoms such as eye pain and double vision, along with sexual, intestinal and urinary system dysfunction, dizziness, and depression. Generally MS is detected between the ages of 20 and 40 years, but less than 1% can occur in childhood and approximately 2-10% after 50 years of age [4,5].

This pathologic condition affects women more than men (sex ratio 2.5:1) and the prevalence varies by geographic area, ranging from 120 per 100,000 individuals [6,7]. The etiology of MS remains unclear, however it can be considered a multifactorial disease and include a genetic predisposition combined with environmental influences [8].

Less is known about the prevalence of multiple sclerosis in non-European populations, with most data indicating lower prevalence in individuals of East Asian and African descent [9]. However, recent studies have observed a higher prevalence in African-American populations, similar to those with European ancestry [9]. Multiple sclerosis demonstrates a prevalence gradient based on latitude, with higher prevalence in northern latitudes of Europe and North America. Additionally, observations have noted variable genetic susceptibility factors among different human subpopulations, apart from latitude, suggesting poorly understood genetic factors interacting with environmental influences.

Several studies have highlighted that populations migrating to regions with higher multiple sclerosis prevalence during childhood also adopt a higher risk of acquiring multiple sclerosis [10]. However, other studies have raised doubts about

this observation [11]. Neither genetic nor external risk factors can solely account for the epidemiological patterns seen in multiple sclerosis. Notably, multiple sclerosis stands as the leading cause of permanent disability among young adults.[12] One study reported an incidence rate of pediatric-acquired multiple sclerosis at 0.51 per 100,000 person-years [13].

Classic MS signs and symptoms are as follows:

- Sensory loss (ie, paresthesias): Usually an early complaint
- Spinal cord symptoms (motor): Muscle cramping secondary to spasticity
- Spinal cord symptoms (autonomic): Bladder, bowel, and sexual dysfunction
- Cerebellar symptoms: Charcot triad of dysarthria (scanning speech), nystagmus, and intention tremor
- Optic neuritis
- Trigeminal neuralgia: Bilateral facial weakness or trigeminal neuralgia
- Facial myokymia (irregular twitching of the facial muscles): May also be a presenting symptom
- Eye symptoms: Including diplopia on lateral gaze (33% of patients)
- Heat intolerance
- Constitutional symptoms: Especially fatigue (70% of cases) and dizziness
- Pain: Occurs in 30–50% of patients at some point in their illness
- Subjective cognitive difficulties: With regard to attention span, concentration, memory, and judgment
- Depression: A common symptom
- Euphoria: Less common than depression
- Bipolar disorder or frank dementia: May be a late finding but is sometimes found at initial diagnosis

Specifically, cognitive impairment can affect up to 70% of patients with MS [14], it has been reported at all phases and all subtypes of the disease [15]; even though it is more frequent in the secondary progressive type [16]; and is a major cause of neurological disability in young and middle-aged adults. The severity and type of cognitive impairment varies considerably among individuals and can be observed in early and in later stages of the disease [17,18]. The areas which have commonly shown more deficits are: information processing speed, episodic memory, complex attention, and executive function [16,19]. There are cognitive domains such social cognition [20], and moral cognition [21,22], which have been less explored in patients with MS.

Cognitive decline reduces the work productivity of these patients and can have great effect in the quality of life of the persons with MS which can also be impaired by the effects the disease has in other areas [23].

In patients with MS and cognitive impairment an alteration both in the white matter (WM) and in the gray matter (GM) of the brain has been found (18–20). However, the complete etiology remains unclear, as little is still known about their

relative contribution to the underpinning process of cognitive impairment. There is a generally poor correlation between the symptoms of cognitive impairment and the conventional MRI measures of structural damage [24].

The assessment of cognitive function in routine clinical practice is still undervalued, despite a lot of published and validated cognitive tests and batteries. It is necessary that clinical neurologists know the need and benefits of performing cognitive assessments in patients with MS routinely [25]. Standardized neurological examinations may be unable to detect emerging cognitive deficits and self-reported cognitive complaints by the patients [26], which can also be confounded by other subjective symptoms, such as depression and anxiety [27]. It is therefore paramount to include an early screening that detects impaired cognition in patients with MS. This could allow for an earlier intervention, which would also include a better psychoeducation and specific work with patients with MS and their families [28].

Depression in MS affects approximately 37–54% of patients, being the most frequently diagnosed psychiatric disorder in the disease, with an estimated risk of occurrence of 50%, compared to 10–15% in the normal population [29].

Its etiology is usually considered multifactorial. Depression is also more frequent in MS than in other chronic diseases that in a similar way cause physical or cognitive disability, so there must be other associated causes to explain their occurrence. Although results from several studies have shown that depression is associated with neuropsychological functioning in MS patients, other investigations have not found this association. Different studies have shown that depressive disorders are more frequent in patients with cognitive impairment. The association of cognitive dysfunction and depression leads to worse results in different neuropsychological tests than those without a depressive symptomatology [30].

Depression in MS may involve different neuropsychobiological mechanisms and it is postulated that the existence (or not) of coping strategies could be a crucial factor. An explanatory model has been proposed, taking into account variables such as social support, coping strategies, stress, self-knowledge and perception of the disease, all of which would influence modulating the onset of depression [31]. Patients affected with MS and cognitive impairment and with major depressive symptomatology use few coping strategies and, on the contrary, employ a high degree of negative coping or avoidance strategies.

Depression affects many aspects of cognitive function in MS, which include working memory, information processing speed, learning functions, abstract reasoning, and executive functioning, so improvement of depression could improve the functioning of patients in these aspects [32].

The depressive symptomatology is closely related to the reduction of the patient's quality of life, causes greater absenteeism and reduces adherence to treatment.

Compared with depression, anxiety is a poorly studied symptom in MS with few studies evaluating the relationship between anxiety and cognitive performance. Its prevalence is estimated to be between 12 and 40%. It has been associated with the presence of fatigue, pain, degree of disability, rates of suicidal ideation, and little adherence to treatment [33].

Anxiety is also known to result from a combination of biological and psychosocial factors. Biological factors associated with anxiety, in general, points to abnormal neuronal circuitry involving the amygdala, basal ganglia, and cerebral cortex and a host of neurotransmitter systems [34]. With regard to psychosocial factors, individuals with MS who suffer from anxiety are more likely to be female, have a shorter disease duration, lower disability levels, younger age of onset, and a lifetime diagnosis of depression.² A higher rate of substance abuse, greater social stress, and limited social support are also known contributors. The consequences of anxiety are similar to depression, particularly, decreased quality of life, poor adherence.

Despite their high comorbidity, research surrounding depression in MS is much more extensive. This may be in part due to the assumption that depression in MS has a greater biological etiology and is just “typical” as it has been reported as far back as Charcot’s descriptions of patients.³⁹ However, anxiety has been purported to be highly underrated in MS, and overshadowed by depression.³⁰ It is surprising that anxiety is not given as much consideration in MS as we know that stress,²⁹ perceived negative consequences, and intolerance of uncertainty⁴⁰ all lie at the foundation of the experience of anxiety. As stated earlier, by virtue of its nature, MS can greatly exacerbate these feelings given its uncertainty and variability – this may be particularly true early on in the disease process, which has been previously shown.

In conclusion, neuropsychological disorders, including cognitive impairment, depression, and anxiety, are common in multiple sclerosis and significantly impact patients’ daily lives. Cognitive deficits, such as reduced processing speed, memory difficulties, and executive dysfunction, can interfere with work and social functioning. In patients with multiple sclerosis, cognitive functions, depression, and anxiety are assessed using neuropsychological tests and evaluated in relation to the clinical course of the disease. Additionally, MRI examinations are used to study the location of demyelination foci in the brain and their association with neuropsychological impairments. This approach helps to gain a deeper understanding of the neurological and psychological aspects of the disease, facilitating early diagnosis and effective treatment.

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